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Review of “An effective parameterization of texture-induced viscous anisotropy in orthotropic materials with application for modeling geodynamical flows”

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Authors Dear Editor,

We wish to thank you and the reviewers for your comments and suggestions. We have revised the manuscript accordingly. A detailed summary of our response to each of the reviewers’ comments is made below. We believe that we have complied with each of the reviewers’ requests, to the greatest extent possible, and look forward to your response concerning the publication of our manuscript.

1 Reviewer 1 (Neil Ribe)

Reviewer The authors present a simple and computationally efficient parameterization of anisotropic rheology for olivine-dominated rocks in the upper mantle. The anisotropy is represented using a Hill yield function whose coefficients are determined by comparison with predictions of the second-order viscoplastic self-consistent (SO-VPSC) polycrystal model. The parameterization is then introduced into a finite-element (FEM) flow code. The authors show that the predictions of the FEM and SO-VPSC methods agree closely for simple test deformations, and demonstrate that including anisotropic rheology costs no more than a factor of ~ 2:5 in computation time. The manuscript ends with a simple application to a fossil shear zone on a continental plate.

The subject of the manuscript is timely, and the work is carefully and convincingly done. My main suggestions (indicated below by page to the nearest tenth of a page) concern the writing: there are too many terms and discussions that will only be understood by experts, and the manuscript could be better organized. I recommend publication after relatively minor revisions.

Authors We thank the reviewer for his/her comments and suggestions.

Reviewer Introduction. The first paragraph is too terse to provide a proper introduction to the subject for non-experts. Please define “texture”, and explain that it is produced by dislocation creep but not by diffusion creep.

Authors The paragraph was modified to better present the context to a non-specialist reader.

Reviewer p. 3.2 Define “analytical yield functions”. Again, you are not writing with non-expert readers in

- mind.
- Authors** The term is explained.
- Reviewer** p. 3.3. The "virtual-experiment strategy" is not clearly described. Non-expert readers will not understand what "fine-scale simulations" and "large-scale simulations" are.
- Authors** The paragraph was rewritten taken into account this remark.
- Reviewer** p. 3.4 "loci-surface": another term that will defeat non-experts.
- Authors** The term was replaced and the sentence rewritten
- Reviewer** p. 4.2. It seems odd to describe the thermo-mechanical code before the SO-VPSC model; the latter is logically prior. I strongly suggest inverting the order of the discussion.
- Authors** We agree with the reviewer that the microscale model is often described before the macroscale model. However, in the present case, we believe that presenting the finite element model first, then the anisotropic constitutive model is more natural. A major reason for presenting the macroscale model first is that although the Hill parameters are here obtained using the second order Viscoplastic Self-consistent (SO-VPSC) model, the proposed parameterization is a general one for anisotropic elastoviscous materials with an orthorhombic symmetry; it does not depend on the method used for calibrating the Hill coefficients. Thus, we decided to keep the original outline of the manuscript.
- Reviewer** p. 5.1 The symbols R and U are not defined.
- Authors** The symbols have been defined.
- Reviewer** p. 5.1 "hypoelastic" is not defined.
- Authors** The definition of "hypoelastic material" has been included in the revised manuscript as a footnote.
- Reviewer** p. 6.1 "equivalent stress" not defined.
- Authors** The sentence was rewritten indicating the equation that defines the term 'equivalent stress'
- Reviewer** Comment 9: p. 6.3 "Von Mises yield function" not defined.
- Authors** The definition of "Von Mises yield function", including a short comment, has been included in the revised manuscript, a footnote has been inserted.
- Reviewer** p. 7.9 p is not defined.
- Authors** The mistake was corrected.
- Reviewer** p. 9.2, section 2.2.3. This section breaks the flow of the argument, and should be put in an Appendix.
- Authors** As it is suggested by the reviewer we moved the section 2.2.3 - Validation of the implemented Hill-based parameterization of the viscoelastic anisotropy - to Appendix I.
- Reviewer** p. 13.3-13.4 The symbol UT appears in eqn. (25), but the symbol U is referred to in the following sentence. Also, what does "power" mean two lines further down?
- Authors** The mistake in the symbol U was corrected. The sentence was modified, the term 'power' was replaced by 'energy'.
- Reviewer** p. 14.0 Equipotencial ! Equipotential
- Authors** Corrected.
- Reviewer** p. 16, Algorithm 1. Personally, I don't find this presentation very helpful. If you want to keep it, please add a prose description of the steps (for strain-rate or stress sampling, not both) with more explanatory detail than is possible to include in Algorithm 1.
- Authors** Considering also your comment 2 (about p. 3.2), we decided not to include in the ms the algorithm detailing the procedure for evaluating the polycrystal equipotential surface.

Reviewer p. 21, fig. 3. It's nice that the results of the models Adeli3D-anis and SO-VPSC agree so well. But what does the agreement really mean? Given the way the authors have formulated the models, is it even possible for the two results to disagree significantly? Put another way, what particular aspect(s) of the models are validated by the good agreement shown in fig. 3? Some discussion of these points would be helpful.

Authors We think that figures 1 and 2 (figures 2 and 3 in the original version of the manuscript) should be viewed as a whole. Figure 1 shows that the equipotential surfaces obtained using a strain-rate or stress points sampling and the SO-VPSC approach for the different shear projections can be described by an elliptical shape (Hill model). In addition, the direct comparison between the results obtained by ADELI-anis and SO-VPSC shows that quantitatively the two solutions present an excellent agreement. Indeed, as mentioned, in this particular case, where the equipotential surface obtained by SO-VPSC and the corresponding HILL present a good agreement, a difference in the anisotropy predicted by both models is not expected. However, although expected, the agreement is not guaranteed a priori and must be verified. The results in figure 2 (previous Fig. 3) confirm that the Hill anisotropy model is suitable for describing the viscous anisotropy of an olivine polycrystal with an orthotropic texture. In addition, they allow discussing the importance of the definition of the applied boundary conditions when comparing finite element and SO-VPSC results.

Reviewer p. 22.5 "Its first application in geodynamics": what is being referred to here? I don't see a reference.

Authors The mistake was corrected.

Reviewer p. 23, fig. 4. Please emphasize in the main text that these are not time-dependent solutions with texture evolution.

Authors The precision was added in the revised manuscript.

2 Reviewer 2 (Dazhi Jiang)

Reviewer In this manuscript, the authors presented a mathematical formulation for the viscous anisotropy of orthorhombic materials arising from CPO development and implemented the formulation numerically. It is particularly significant that they used Hill's orthotropic yield criterion to define the anisotropy and described a novel method of using the SO-VPSC model to determine the six coefficients.

They implemented the formulation in a 3D thermo-mechanical finite-element code to model large-scale geodynamical flows where they considered a Maxwell rheology combining isotropic elasticity with anisotropic non-linear viscous behaviors. The implementation was also validated with analytical solutions and the SO-VPSC model for simple shear.

I find this approach very interesting and significant for 3D geodynamical models where evolving anisotropic viscosities must be considered in the deformation of lithospheric materials like olivine polycrystals. Rocks with texture are so common in Earth's lithosphere. Geodynamic models have been suffering from too simplistic rheological models and single-scaled treatment. It is encouraging to learn that their implementation of the formulation is not computationally too expensive, as is often the case when anisotropy and/or multiscale problems are addressed. Their test application in this article already showed significant coupling effects between localized deformation due to olivine CPO in the mantle and the mechanical behavior of the elasto-viscoplastic overlying crust.

I suggest that the manuscript be accepted for publication with only some minor modification suggested in the following specific comments, mainly to improve the accessibility of the paper to the general geology community. I did not find any shared software scripts used in the implementation and hope they will be made available.

Authors We are thankful to the reviewer for the comments and suggestions

Reviewer "Geodynamical flows produce strong olivine textures, which are only significantly modified by further deformation". Textures may get stronger or weaker by continuous progressive

deformation or deformation overprinting.

Authors We agree with the reviewer and added a short phrase indicating that a new deformation may not only strengthen but also weaken a texture

Reviewer You write of “texture-induced anisotropy” and this is the anisotropy your formulation is about. Perhaps add a brief discussion on what else can give rise to viscous anisotropy.

Authors We feel that discussion of other possible causes of viscous anisotropy in rocks, like the formation of a compositional layering, which are not treated in the present work, may confound more than enlighten the reader. So we prefer not to do it.

Reviewer “Hierarchical multi-scale modelling provides a path for exchanging information between systems with different characteristic length scales.” I fully agree that ‘Hierarchical multi-scale modelling’ is a right approach toward multiscale problems. My work toward multiscale deformation and fabric formation through an “inclusion within inclusion” application of micromechanics is precisely such a “hierarchical multi-scale” approach (Jiang and Bentley, 2012; Jiang 2014, 2016; Jiang and Bhandari, 2018).

Authors The comment is greatly appreciated. There are many points in common between our works, which are clearly complementary.

Reviewer It will be helpful if you give at least one textbook reference for your equation 2 on the Jaumann and Green-Naghdi derivatives. For instance, when is the Green-Naghdi derivative relevant?

Authors We agree with the suggestion of the reviewer. A couple of references were added.

- Malver, L.E., Introduction to the Mechanics of a Continuous Medium, Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1969.
- Johnson, G.C. and Bammann, D.J., A discussion of stress rates in finite deformation problems, Int. J. Solids. Struct., 20 (1984) 725-737

Reviewer I guess “equivalent stress, $J(\sigma)$ ” is a scalar function of the deviatoric (?) stress tensor? A little more description will help the general geoscience readers who are not familiar with the subject. “Fluidity” is also not generally used in the geoscience literature. Please simply point out that it is the inverse of viscosity.

Authors The reviewer comment on this point has been appreciated. The definition of $J(\sigma)$, including a short comment, has been included in the revised manuscript, a footnote has been inserted. A brief remarking on the term “Fluidity” has also been included.

Reviewer It is very helpful when you pointed out that the Hill criterion builds on and is like the extension of von Mises’ criterion to orthorhombic materials.

Reviewer Section 2.2.1 is great, brief and clear!

Authors Both reviewer’s comments are greatly appreciated.

Reviewer You pointed out the values of G, F, H, L, M, N when the material is isotropic. What are the values when the material is cubic?

Authors The value of the coefficients F, G, H, L, M, and N refer to the anisotropy of the permanent deformation of the material. The value of these coefficients depends on the crystalline structure of the material (i.e., cubic, hexagonal, orthorhombic, etc.) but it is not the symmetry the main factor that determines the value. The crystallographic preferred orientations (CPO or texture) is one of the key factor, together with the crystal slip systems and its contrast (CRSS, Critical Resolved Shear Stress) that relate crystal anisotropy with polycrystal anisotropy.

For example, in the ideal case of having a polycrystalline olivine aggregate, where all the crystals do not show a preferentiality in their orientations, although the crystal is highly anisotropic, the HILL-coefficients, which reflect the behavior of the polycrystal, are those of an isotropic material.

Reviewer Change “Assuming D and ω constant in the time interval...” to either “Assuming D and ω are

constant in the time interval..” or “Assuming constant D and ω in the time interval..”

Authors The reviewer’s observation has been taken into account and the manuscript updated.

Reviewer “Defining \mathcal{R} as the laboratory reference frame and \mathcal{R} the material reference frame”. You are actually talking about coordinate systems not reference frames.

Reviewer “Normally in Materials Sciences, these coefficients are determined through a set of mechanical tests. However, such tests are often unfeasible for geological materials. because viscous deformation is only attained experimentally at high confining pressures, limiting the possible geometry of laboratory experiments. Thus, we calibrated the Hill coefficients, which describe the texture-induced viscous anisotropy of olivine polycrystals, based on VPSC polycrystal plasticity simulations.”

Yes! I cannot imagine that orthorhombic viscosity coefficients can be determined purely experimentally. Determining F, G, H, L, M, N by least-square fitting of four equipotential surfaces calculated using the SO-VPSC model is a good idea.

Authors We agree with the reviewer’s comment; the meaning could be misinterpreted. The sentence has been modified.

Reviewer I have used tangent and affine approaches. Good to know that second order approximation is important for olivine. A student of mine is using VPSC7c SO to simulate quartz polycrystals.

Authors It is now established that the tangent approximation does not correctly account for the mechanical interaction between grains. They are a couple of papers of Castelnau and Lebenshon that discuss in detail this issue. The main difference arises from the fact that intragranular strain heterogeneity is not taken, which it is present in SO approximations. Likewise, SO results approach very well the results obtained by full- field FFT models, for example. In general, as the contrast in the deformation mechanics increase, (i.e. CRSS of hard modes is several times much higher than the CRSS of the easy mode, presence of void, etc.) it is recommended to use SO models. This is clearly the case for olivine. The recommendation should also be valid for quartz, at least at low temperature, where basal slip clearly predominates.

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